

Indicators Assessing Water Quality at Rubber Latex Processing Factories

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Abstract:

Water is an indispensable component of human life, so if the water quality meets the standards, it will help protect the health, increase fitness and lead a happier, happier life. On the contrary, if the quality of water we use does not meet the standards, it will easily cause life-threatening illnesses for our family members and us. In Vietnam, there are two main sources of water: groundwater and surface water. Due to the climate and production characteristics of rubber processing plants, all the water near these factories contains a lot of inorganic and organic impurities, microorganisms, dissolved gas, heavy metals. This makes the watercolor opaque, colored, smells fishy, foul very difficult to use. To assess the level of water pollution, we provide criteria to assess water quality.

Keywords: Water quality, rubber processing, Vietnam.

I. Physical criteria

1. Color (color)

In general, clean natural water is colorless, allowing sunlight to reach deep aquifers. Water is only colored because of the presence of some organic substances and iron (III) compounds. Wastewater may have different shades. In many cases, the color of the water is caused by microorganisms, mud particles, aquatic plants, sulfides, suspended substances.

2. Temperature

The temperature of natural water depends on the climatic conditions, the weather of the basin or the surrounding environment. Industrial wastewater especially that of thermal power plants and nuclear power plants, often has higher temperatures than natural water in catchment basins, so it causes water to heat up (heat pollution).

The high temperature of the water changes the biological, chemical and physical processes of a water ecosystem. Some creatures will not tolerate dying or have to move to other places, while others thrive. The high temperature of the water can also significantly affect the air environment (more humid, fog.) The temperature of the water can be determined by using a digital thermometer to instantly measure the temperature of the water, preferably directly at the source.

3. Electric Conductivity

The conductivity of water is related to the presence of ions in water, such as Na^+ , SO_4^{2-} , NO_3^- . Pure water hardly conducts electricity because the water dissociates very little. These substances dissolve in water, dissociating into ions so that natural water and sewage conduct electricity. To determine the conductivity of water, resistance is measured or a direct conductivity meter with a measurement of micromen per meter (mS / m). The conductivity of water is compared with the conductivity of the KCl solution. At 25°C:

+ KCl 10^{-3} M solution has a corresponding conductivity of 141 mS / m.

+ KCl 10^{-2} M solution has a corresponding conductivity of 147.3 mS / m.

+ KCl $5 \cdot 10^{-2}$ M solution with a corresponding conductivity of 666.8 mS / m.

+ KCl 10^{-1} M solution has a corresponding conductivity of 1290.0 mS / m.

Typical conductivity of some types of water:

- + Pure water: 5.5. 10⁻⁶ S / m
- + Ordinary drinking water: 0.005 - 0.05 S / m
- + Sea water 5 S / m

4. Turbidity

Clean natural water usually does not contain suspended solids, so it is transparent and colorless. Water turbidity is the level of preventing light from passing through water. Cloudy water is caused by water containing colloidal particles suspended in the water, which can be clay, humus, microorganisms, hydroxides in the form of amorphous colloidal (Fe(OH)₃, Al(OH)₃). High turbidity indicates a high concentration of contamination in water. Opaque water prevents the process of sunlight on the bottom of the water. The solids in water prevent the normal activities of humans and organisms. The turbidity of water is caused by suspended impurities in the water, so the sexuality may be due to the total suspended solids (TSS) in the water with a unit of mg / l, and the unit of measurement is NTU (Nephelometric). Turbidity Units): a unit of diffusion turbidity.

5. Smell

Clean water odorless, tasteless. If the water has an unpleasant taste, it is a symptom of polluted water. The smell of water is caused mainly by the following two reasons:

- + Product breakdown of organic substances in water.
- + Because wastewater contains different substances, the smell of water is specific to each type of wastewater.

The odor of water is determined on a conventional scale, for example, if the water sample smells, dilute with clean water at a ratio of V / V of 1 ÷ 1 and the odor disappears, then the sample has a conventional odor index. equal to 1, and if diluting V / V with 2, 3, 4, 100/1. the smell disappears, then the corresponding odor index equals 2, 3, 4, ... 100 ...

II. The chemical indicators

1. pH level

The pH value of wastewater must be measured immediately after sampling, not later than determination after 4 hours of sampling to determine the pH of the water you can use a pH meter or pH paper.

$$\text{pH} = -\log[\text{H}^+]$$

The change in pH leads to a change in the chemical composition of water (precipitation, solubility, carbonate balance, etc.). The pH value of the water source contributes to the determination of the water treatment method.

2. Acidity, alkalinity of water

- Define:
- + Acidity is the content of substances in water that participate in the reaction with strong alkalis (NaOH, KOH).
- + Alkalinity is the content of substances in the water that react with HCl.
- To determine the acidity or alkalinity of water, a titration is used using the indicator methyl orange or phenolphthalein.

- Determination of acidity. Take V (ml) water (100 ml), add a few drops of indicator phenoltalein or methyl orange, then use the standard solution of NaOH 10^{-2} M to titrate until the solution changes color, use up the a (ml) solution NaOH solution when using methyl orange, b (ml) NaOH solution when using phenolphthalein.

The free acidity (m) and total acidity (p) of a water sample is calculated using the following formula:

$$m = \frac{a \cdot 10^{-2} \cdot 1000}{V} \text{ (mđlg/l)}$$

$$p = \frac{b \cdot 10^{-2} \cdot 1000}{V} \text{ (mđlg/l)}$$

- Determination of alkalinity. Take V (ml) water (100 ml), add 2, 3 drops of phenolphthalein indicator (to determine free alkalinity p) or methyl orange (to determine total alkalinity m) and titrate with HCl 10^{-2} M until the solution changes color, using a (ml) solution of HCl when using phenolphthalein indicator and b (ml) when using methyl orange indicator. The alkalinity of the water sample is calculated by the formula:

$$m = \frac{a \cdot 10^{-2} \cdot 1000}{V} \text{ (mđlg/l)}$$

$$p = \frac{b \cdot 10^{-2} \cdot 1000}{V} \text{ (mđlg/l)}$$

3. Hardness of water

The hardness of water is due to valence alkaline earth metals II mainly calcium and magnesium. It is often distinguished between carbonate hardness and non-carbonate hardness.

+ Carbonate hardness is equivalent to the amount of calcium and magnesium in the form of carbonate salts (hydrocarbons and carbonates). This hardness is easily processed when boiling water, so it is also known as temporary hardness.

+ Non-carbonate hardness is the amount of calcium and magnesium corresponding to the anions of chloride, sulfate, and nitrate. This hardness does not decompose when the water is boiled, hence the name permanent hardness.

The total of these two hardness types is the total hardness of the water.

Hardness is usually expressed as the number of milligrams of the gram (mg) of calcium and magnesium in 1 liter of water. Sugar represents the hardness in mg CaCO₃ in 1 liter of water.

+ Soft water with hardness ≤ 50 mg CaCO₃/l.

+ Hard medium water has a hardness of ~ 150 mg CaCO₃/l.

+ Water with hardness ≥ 300 mg CaCO₃ / l is called too hard.

To determine the hardness of water, often use the titration method of Complexon. The standard solution is EDTA with known concentration of ETOO indicator in buffer medium of NH₃ with pH 8.5 - 10, using CaCN to eliminate the effects of Fe (II), Fe (III), Cu (II) ions , Cd (II), Ni (II), Co (II), ... are in water.

4. The sediment suspended in water

Total suspended solids (TSS mg / l). Take V ml of water (500 ml) to run through a filter membrane dried at 100 - 105 ° C and weigh as m₁ grams. After the sample has run out, wash the membrane with clean distilled water. Take the film to dry at 100 - 105 °C and weigh m₂ m₂.

$$\text{TSS} = \frac{m_2 - m_1}{V} \cdot 1000 \text{ (g/l)} = \frac{m_2 - m_1}{V} \cdot 10^6 \text{ (mg/l)}$$

Suspended solids are solids suspended in water. The suspended solids (SS) content is the dry mass of the remaining solids on a glass fiber filter when filtering 1 liter of water through a Gut filter funnel and drying at 100 -105 ° C, in mg / l.

Dissolved solids (DS) is the difference between total solids content and suspended solids content.

$$DS = TSS - SS \text{ (mg / l)}$$

Volatile solids (VS). The volatile solids content is the mass lost after heating SS suspension at 550°C to constant mass, in mg / l or%. The content of volatile solids in wastewater usually represents the content of organic matter in water. The solid can be deposited and the volume (in ml) of the solids portion of 1 liter of water to settle for 1 hour, in mg / l.

5. Determination of dissolved oxygen in water (DO- Winkler method)

Dissolved oxygen is an important hydrological factor that determines the intensity of a series of biochemical processes and is also an indicator of water mass.

- The higher the DO, the higher the algae water and the lower the organic content.

- Determination method: - pp Winkler (chemical pp)

-pp measure oxygen electrode dissolved oxygen meter

- The principle of this method is that in an alkaline environment (pH 9 -10), add MnSO₄ to the water sample, shake well, the Mn²⁺ ion will be dissolved in water oxidized to Mn (IV), take the dissolved precipitate into acid, in the presence of excess I⁻ then Mn (IV) will oxidize I⁻ to release I₂. Using Na₂S₂O₃ solution to titrate the amount of I₂ released with a starch indicator, we will calculate the DO value in the water sample.

Reactions

The formula for calculating DO:

$$DO = \frac{V_{Na_2S_2O_3}^{ml} N_{Na_2S_2O_3} V_{O_2}^{(=8)}}{V} \times 1000 \text{ (mgO}_2\text{/l)}$$

(V is the volume of a water sample taken for analysis)

6. Determination of biochemical oxygen demand (BOD)

BOD is the amount of oxygen needed to oxidize organic matter in water by microorganisms.

Therefore, BOD is the most common indicator to determine the level of water pollution, it is typical for the amount of organic matter that can be oxidized by VSV in water. When biological oxidation occurs, VSVs use the amount of dissolved oxygen present in water (DO).

The process of biological oxidation occurs very slowly and lasts. In fact, the decomposition of organic compounds in water by VSV is very relevant. Therefore, people often use this indicator to assess the pollution of organic matter of water. However, it is not possible to determine the amount of oxygen required for VSV to completely oxidize the organic matter in water, but only the amount of oxygen needed when incubated at 20°C

in a dark chamber (to avoid the process). photosynthesis of plants in water, this process will produce oxygen) in 5 days, when only about 70 -80% of organic matter is oxidized. If all the experiments were conducted at the same conditions and time, the results would still be used to assess the pollution level of organic matter in water accurately. Therefore, the result is expressed as BOD₅ (5 here means incubation for 5 days of oxidation VSV). If the incubation period lasts up to 25 days, it will only oxidize 95% of organic matter, not completely.

III. Biological indicators

In natural water, especially in wastewater, there are many types of bacteria, viruses, algae and protozoa. They enter the water from the surrounding environment; they live and grow in the water.

The harmful microorganisms are germs that cause diseases from garbage sources, human and animal diseases such as cholera, typhoid, polio, helminthes. E-coli bacteria are characteristic bacteria of the level of infection of water. E-coli index is the number of bacteria in 1 liter of water (running water must have E-coli index <20)

The algae and protozoans present in the water make the watercolored when rotting, it will increase the amount of organic matter in the water. These organic (biodegradable) organic matter will consume oxygen, causing the water to lack oxygen, affecting aquatic organisms.

References

- i. Geogre J.K. and Yuan B. - *The fuzzy sets and fuzzy logic: theory and applications*, New Jersey, Prentice Hall Inc, 1995, p. 1-5.
- ii. Jiang J. and Xiao Y. - *Assessing water quality using fuzzy theory and information entropy in Baiyangdian, China, International Symposium on Water Resource and Environmental Protection 1 (2011)*, p. 1047 - 1050.
- iii. Sijing F., et al. - *Fuzzy comprehensive evaluation for urban surface water pollution risk, Bioinformatics and Biomedical Engineering, International Conference on 3 (2009) p.1- 4*
- iv. Li P. and Jian-Hua W. - *Application of set pair analysis method based on entropy weight in groundwater quality assessment - a case study in Dongsheng City, Northwest China, Journal of Chemistry 8 (2011) p. 851- 858.*
- v. Yang L. and Wu S. - *Using variable fuzzy set theory and information entropy for air pollution risk assessment in Beijing, China, 2011 2nd International Conference on Environmental Science and Development 4 (2011) p. 33 - 41.*
- vi. Liu W. and Cui J. - *Entropy coefficient method to evaluate the level of sustainable development of China's sports, International Journal of Sports Science and Engineering 2 (2008) p. 72-78.*